

IMPACT OF INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEES' GREEN VOICE BEHAVIOR IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING CULTURE

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to examine how inclusive leadership (IL) affects employees' green voice behavior (EGVB) in the hospitality sector, with an emphasis on the mediating function of organizational learning culture (OLC) in Bangladesh's travel and tourist business. Based on Social Learning Theory and Social Exchange Theory, the study creates and evaluates a model that connects learning culture, employees' green voice behavior, and leadership behaviors. Convenience sampling was used to collect data from hotel staff in popular tourist locations including Dhaka and Chittagong, and 278 valid replies were obtained. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was used to examine the data. Results show that IL promotes corporate learning culture and significantly improves workers' green voice behavior. All four hypotheses were supported. The study contributes to the growing body of literature on leadership and sustainability in the hospitality sector, while offering practical insights for managers to cultivate IL and strengthen learning-oriented cultures to promote environmentally responsible employee engagement.

Keywords: Inclusive Leadership, Employees' green voice behavior, Orgnsizational learning culture, SET, PLS-SEM

1. Introduction

Environmental concerns have attracted international attention in recent decades (Ding et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2025). Since businesses contribute significantly to environmental challenges, they are inevitably under pressure from governments, shareholders, and customers (Irfan et al., 2024). More companies are putting green management procedures, guidelines, and systems into place in response to these environmental concerns (Yu et al., 2023). However, depending solely on these formal

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organizational measures from the top is inadequate (Nas et al., 2021) due to the complexity of environmental challenges (Iqbal et al., 2024). Most green initiatives depend on workers' voluntary involvement outside of their assigned tasks (Liu & Qi, 2022). Because the hospitality industry often lacks the means to solve environmental challenges, it is imperative that firms encourage workers to actively and freely participate in green activities.

While little is known about employees' green voice behavior (EGVB), researchers are currently primarily interested in extra-role behaviors or organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB) toward the environment (Gu & Liu, 2022). EGVB is an eco-friendly, voluntary behavior that involves proposing new, environmentally friendly ideas and pushing for modifications to current procedures even in the face of opposition (Al-Romeedy & Badwy, 2025). Since employees viewed voice as an expensive and detrimental activity that may make them look like opponents or troublemakers, since it usually challenges the status quo, exploring different aspects that inspire EGVB becomes an essential area of research (Nazeer et al., 2025).

Prior research on EGVB mostly concentrated on corporate social responsibility (Crucke et al., 2022; Shah et al., 2021), green practices such as human resource management (Z. Liu et al., 2024; Murillo-Ramos et al., 2024), and mindfulness (Kim et al., 2017; Murillo-Ramos et al., 2024). However, there is a dearth of studies on how leadership fosters EGVB (Aboramadan et al., 2024; Crucke et al., 2022). Leadership has been found to have a substantial impact on employee attitudes, values, and behaviors (Alwheshi et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024; Siyal et al., 2023). Research has proven that leadership has a noteworthy influence on voice behavior (Ilyas et al., 2021; C. Liu et al., 2023; W. Liu et al., 2010).

In response to calls for more research on this issue (Crucke et al., 2022; Ilyas et al., 2022), we employed social exchange theory (SET) (Bandura & Walters, 1977) to explore the impact of leadership on EGVB because of their large and direct influence on employees through regular contact. Businesses require IL that improves employee satisfaction due to the difficulty and challenges of tackling environmental issues. This includes reducing the perceived risks of taking initiative (Shafaei et al., 2024), fostering a sense of competence and autonomy (Siyal et al., 2023), raising feelings of uniqueness and belonging (Adams et al., 2020), and promoting positive relationships between leaders and employees (Li et al., 2024). Additionally, at the individual and corporate levels, IL promotes sustainability and lowers resource use. Likewise, inclusive leaders provide workers with a sense of psychological empowerment, which leads to increased levels of autonomy at work that are further mirrored in workers' behavior, which includes a variety of eco-friendly practices (Jha et al., 2025).

Moreover, we propose the organizational learning culture (OLC) as a mechanism that explains the relationship between IL and EGVB based on SLT. According to Nejati and Shafaei (2023), it makes sense to suggest that IL support OLC, which encourages staff members to practice environmentally friendly behavior and share their thoughts and recommendations on environmental issues (Khan & Terason, 2022). However,

very few studies have been conducted on EGVB in the hospitality sector, and most of the studies are based on developed economies. Also, there is limited empirical research on how inclusive leaders promote green voice behavior, and how the OLC mediates such a relationship.

The study on EGVB is significant in the context of Bangladesh's hospitality industry. Bangladesh is fortunate to have the world's longest sea beach, Cox's Bazar, coral islands Saint Martin's, and the world's largest mangrove forest, the Sundarbans. Furthermore, it provides opportunities to witness the breathtaking sunsets and sunrises from Kuakata, the lush green tea plantations of Sylhet, the green hills and mountains of the Chittagong Hill Tracts with their streams and valleys, and many more. Traditional events, such as PahelaBaishakh (the first day of spring) and Nababarsha (Bengali New Year), attract travelers from all over the world. These festivals entice travelers with their colorful vibes while also sharing the history, heritage, and friendliness of this wonderful country's people, and as a result, tourism has become an essential economic component of most people's lives in Bangladesh.

Additionally, given the potential to achieve multiple Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), tourism is recognized as one of Bangladesh's thrust industries, establishing a definitive relationship between tourism and sustainability. However, it will be challenging unless the human resources related to tourism voice concerns about the sustainable practices. Therefore, this study focuses on EGVB reflected by employees' insights that can shape internal operations, strategic sustainability planning, and broader ecological stewardship in the hospitality sector.

Here, Dhaka and Chittagong were focused on the study since they have a diverse array of hotels, both locally owned and multinational brands. While Chittagong exhibits a mix of business, transit, and leisure travel, Dhaka mostly symbolizes urban and business tourism. Again, significant environmental constraints, including excessive energy consumption, water scarcity, waste management problems, and urban pollution, are faced by hotels in Dhaka and Chittagong. Due to the resource-intensive nature of hospitality operations, these issues are more noticeable. As a result, these cities offer a valuable setting for researching sustainability concepts where environmental improvements are significant, such as EGVB, and leadership for sustainability.

Therefore, this study expects to contribute to both theory and practice by responding to the focal research question about whether inclusive leadership (IL) impacts the employee green voice behavior (EGVB) and whether organizational learning culture (OLC) plays any role for stimulating such nexus. Based on this fundamental purpose, this study focuses on the following specific research questions:

- RQ 1: To what extent does inclusive leadership (IL) influence the employee green voice behavior (EGVB)?
- RQ 2: To what degree does organizational learning culture (OLC) mediate the relationship between inclusive leadership (IL) and employee green voice behavior (EGVB)?

In fact, this study addresses the following specific research objectives:

- to evaluate the effects of inclusive leadership (IL) on employee green voice behavior (EGVB);
- to examine the influence of IL on organizational learning culture (OLC);
- to investigate the nexus between OLC and EGVB;
- to assess the indirect mediating effects of OLC on the relationship between IL and EGVB in Bangladesh's hospitality industry; and
- to provide suggestions for future research in the hospitality sector that could assist stakeholders in fostering sustainability.

2. Underlying Theories and Hypotheses

2.1 Social Exchange Theory (SET): A useful foundation for explaining the EGVB in this study could be provided by SET (Blau, 1964), which can serve as a framework to justify such exchanges between the inclusive leader and the followers' green voice behavior. According to SET, employees will view a leader favorably if they are seen as inclusive, open, accessible, and available (Carmeli et al., 2010), which ultimately leads to a desire on the part of the employees to reciprocate by acting in extra-role activities, such as using green voice behaviors. According to Carmeli et al. (2010) and Choi et al. (2015), inclusive leaders are very interested in the expectations and feelings of their staff and consider team members' differences and support their belongingness to facilitate each team member's contributions, such as stimulating team members to voice their ideas and perspectives in the team (Ashikali et al., 2021). Additionally, IL enhances employees' voluntary communicative efforts to acquire and circulate tasks and managerial information and to share and discuss positive and negative aspects of their organization with internal members (Lee, 2022). Therefore, due to reciprocity, even if engaging in voice is risky, due to the support, fairness, and voice opportunities provided by IL employees make them more willing to take such risks.

2.2 Social Learning Theory (SLT): According to Bandura's (1977) SLT, people acquire knowledge from the people they socialize with through observation, modelling, and the interaction of personal, behavioral and environmental factors. SLT, therefore, provides a strong theoretical bridge between an organization's learning culture and employees' pro-environmental behaviors (Bandura, 1986), like EGVB. According to SLT, followers look up to leaders as role models, and the actions of these leaders have an impact on their followers. Therefore, when inclusive leaders model green behavior and explain the rationale, employees attend, encode, and imitate those behaviors (Hu et al., 2022). SLT elucidates the impact of IL by examining how employees observe and replicate the behavior exhibited by leaders, which further reinforces OLC that legitimizes environmental voice (Thabet et al., 2024). Leaders exemplify reflexivity and empowerment, thereby facilitating followers' acquisition of self-efficacy in articulating sustainability-oriented ideas within a nurturing culture that promotes shared knowledge and adaptability (Alqatan et al., 2025).

2.3 IL and EGVB Association: EGVB is a pro-environmental action that is both demanding and motivating, as Sibunruang & Kawai (2024) perceived it as a proactive activity that is future-oriented and beneficial in purpose when it is promotive, while it may be confrontational and change-oriented, potentially harming relationships. EGVB is an eco-friendly and voluntary activity that involves pushing for modifications to current procedures and offering new pro-environmental proposals, even when others disagree (Aboramadan et al., 2021; Murillo-Ramos et al., 2024). Regarding IL, in 2006, Nembhard and Edmondson developed the notion of IL by proposing that leader inclusiveness is defined as words and deeds by a leader or leaders that indicate an invitation and appreciation for others' contributions. According to Carmeli et al. (2010), who built the concept of IL from scratch, leaders who exhibit openness, accessibility, and availability in their interactions with followers represent IL. With that notion, the IL may improve workers' EGVB.

According to the SET (Blau, 1964), inclusive leaders encourage actions to give their staff members the impression that they have been treated well, which encourages them to return the favor to the leader and the company (Hollander, 2009). Meanwhile, according to Sibunruang and Kawai (2024), "faith in leaders is relevant to the leader-directed OCB dimensions of altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, and courtesy." Thus, hospitality organizations must explore IL that improves EGVB. Again, the workforce demonstrates strong dedication to environmental behavior while also maintaining elevated energy levels that lead them to behave positively toward their inclusive leaders (Aboramadan et al. 2022). Such reciprocal motivation, as SET posits, towards their leader and organization leads employees to display green voice behavior (Uzum et al., 2025). Given the above arguments, we propose the following:

H1: IL is positively associated with EGVB.

2.4 IL and OLC Relationship: According to Garvin A. (1994), organizations are considered to have an OLC if they are skilled at producing, gaining, and disseminating knowledge and adapting their behavior to consider fresh information. According to Yang et. al (2004), one of the imperatives that make up an OLC is continuous learning, which involves creating opportunities for all members, promoting inquiry, team learning, empowerment, embedding systems, system connection, and strategic leadership. These practices encourage collaboration, collective vision, global thinking, and support learning at individual, team, and organizational levels (Hanh Tran & Choi, 2019).

The beneficial conditions for promoting OLC emerge because of inclusive leader behavior (Xie, 2019). The SLT (Bandura, 1986) asserts that learning culture may be impacted by the actions of leaders. Inclusive leaders who are approachable and enthusiastic to engage with employees to cultivate a shared vision are essential for a learning-oriented culture (Real et al., 2014). Employees have greater opportunity to accelerate the learning and dissemination of information when a leader fosters the expression of diverse opinions, questions long-held assumptions and beliefs, and

encourages fresh viewpoints (Zagorsek et al., 2009). According to earlier research, executives and staff may clarify organizational goals through an open culture (Zagorsek et al., 2009). Thus, we put forth the following hypothesis.

H2: IL is positively related to OLC.

2.5 Link Between OLC and EGVB: OLC addresses green behavior challenges through efficiency by implementing green thinking into existing knowledge-management operations (Vidal-Salazar et al., 2012). The research shows that organizational learning creates substantial changes to civic virtue and OCB and conscientiousness (Deswal & Sheokand., 2025). Under such learning culture-driven environments, employees gain opportunities to share their information and knowledge with co-workers while embracing different plausible approaches towards continuous organizational advancement (Sidani and Reese, 2018). According to Özgül and Zehir (2019), organizational culture significantly supports employee green actions. In addition, research demonstrates that an OLC connects positively to organizational green conduct and functions as supporting personnel commitment to business targets (Chin, Yean, & Leow, 2021). Based on SLT, an organization with an OLC can establish permanent learning opportunities to enhance knowledge exchange and teamwork, which enables employees to achieve and grow relevant workplace abilities (Meher et al., 2024). However, research needs a more extensive empirical study to understand how OLC works with other workplace variables (Egan et al., 2004; Lin et al., 2019). Thus, we propose the following:

H3: OLC is positively linked to EGVB.

2.6 Role of OLC: A strong OLC enhances the effectiveness of IL in fostering EGVB by creating an environment where individuals feel safe, connected, and empowered to share sustainability-oriented ideas (Hanh Tran & Choi, 2019). IL highly focuses on providing an open culture in which employees can contribute their unique ideas (Nejati & Shafaei, 2023), which promotes organisational knowledge sharing and learning (Guo et al., 2020). And through repeated leader behaviors, employees collectively learn that voicing new ideas is acceptable and valued. This aligns with SLT, which posits that individuals learn appropriate behaviors by observing role models and the consequences of their actions (Bandura, 1977).

Furthermore, a learning-driven, innovative culture fosters openness, flexibility, and creativity, encouraging employees to propose new solutions to environmental challenges (Rohmah et al., 2023). Prior research has similarly shown that learning culture acts as a critical mechanism through which IL influences employee behaviors, such as OCB (Hanh Tran & Choi, 2019). Together, these mechanisms amplify the positive influence of IL, making it more likely that employees will actively engage in pro-environmental voice behaviors like EGVB. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that,

H4: OLC positively mediates the relationship between IL and EGVB.

Therefore, this study develops the theoretical framework as stated in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model

IL: Inclusive Leadership; OLC: Organizational Learning Culture; EGVB: Employees' Green Voice Behavior

3. Methods

3.1 Data: This study adopted a convenience sampling method to collect data from the employees of 30 three-star hotels located in Dhaka and Chittagong district. Convenience sampling is a popular method in quantitative research and was employed when target population members met criteria like being readily available, residing close by, and being eager to take part, all of which are pertinent to our inquiry (Asiamah et al., 2017). Also, hotel selection was made possible by the convenience sampling strategy, which gives researchers faster replies than probability sampling techniques.

An online survey run with Google Forms was used to gather data from December 2024 to March 2025. To ensure the privacy of the participants, this survey did not contain the names or affiliations of the respondents. Employees who held junior to mid-level positions within the company and had at least one year of service experience and understanding of green initiatives were emailed to take part in the study. Because they are immediately involved in day-to-day operations and are therefore most exposed to organizational procedures, environmental routines, and leadership behaviors inside the company, junior and mid-level employees were chosen as respondents. From the standpoint of employee voice, lower-to-middle level employees are more likely to recognize inefficiencies, environmental concerns, and chances for improvement in routine work procedures. Finally, compared to senior bosses, junior and mid-level employees frequently face a higher power imbalance, which makes voice behavior more discretionary and possibly dangerous for them.

A 69% response rate was achieved by receiving 278 responses via Google Forms. The responses comprised 219 males (78%) and 54 females (22%). Over half (54%) of the respondents were between the ages of 26 and 35. The majority of the staff members (67%) had honor's degrees, and the rest of the employees hold a three-year diploma degree. Regarding job experience, 44% of respondents had three to four years, and 27% had less than two years' experience.

3.2 Measurements: To increase validity and reliability, we used to measure scales from well-established scales. EGVB was measured with Liang et al.'s (2016) ten-item scale. The sample item involved "I proactively voice out constructive suggestions ...". The scale and this methodology have been used by Hwang and Lee (2019), Tabrizi et al. (2023) and Nourafkan et al. (2023) for measuring EGVB. IL was assessed using a nine-item scale proposed by Carmeli et al. (2010). A comparable scale was used in earlier research (Choi et al. 2017; Qi et al. 2019). The sample item involved "My manager inspires me to make him/her accessible to emerging matters". Additionally, the scale's reliability rating of 0.951 confirmed its reliability (Shakil et al., 2023). A seven-item scale used by Yang et al. (2004) was adopted for measuring OLC. The sample item involved "In my organization, leaders continually look for opportunities to learn". The seven-item scale shows reliability of 0.880 (Yang et al., 2004).

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques: Smart PLS 4.1.0 was used to study the data and determine if the sample data were representative. SPSS 27 was utilized to conduct the Harman single-factor test. Since the PLS-SEM system does not necessitate a standard assumption test, standard sample data were employed (Hair et al., 2017). The latent nature of the variables, which made direct measurement difficult, supported the use of the PLS-SEM approach. Three variables, EGVB, an endogenous variable, OLC, a mediator, and IL, an exogenous variable, are the main factors of interest in this study. Every measurement technique was assessed using five-point Likert ratings. The measuring model was initially tested in the study to assess the validity and reliability of the constructs. After that, the structural model was examined to confirm the hypotheses.

3.4 Common Method Bias (CMB): The Harman single-factor test for multicollinearity analysis and Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) values were employed to assess CMB (Kyriazos&Poga, 2023). Kock (2015) states that a VIF value of less than 3.3 indicates the absence of multicollinearity. The findings demonstrate that all VIF values fall below this threshold, indicating that multicollinearity is not an issue (see Table 5). According to Harman's one-factor statistical analysis, the first factor's highest variance explanation was 33.31% (see Appendix), which was less than 40% of the overall variance of the data (Cheah et al. 2019; Fuller et al. 2016). Even though only one source was used for data collection, CMB was not an issue. Additionally, to lessen evaluation nervousness, respondents were first given assurances of anonymity and information that there were no right or wrong answers. Then, by putting predictors and criterion variables in different areas of the questionnaire with different instructions, they were kept psychologically separated.

4. Results

4.1 Measurement Model: The association between each indicator and its latent variables was examined through measurement model analysis, including item loadings, reliability and convergent validity. The current study evaluated construct and internal consistency reliability and validity using measurement model testing (see

Table 1). The factor loading should exceed 0.701, α and rho_a should be above 0.700, and the AVE essential to be greater than 0.500 (Hair et al., 2017). Thus, the loading values less than the threshold were removed for the study. Here, the items EGVB1, EGVB3, EGVB8, IL8, and IL9 were deleted due to loading less than 0.701. The factor loadings for the remaining items, α and rho_a, and AVE exceed the threshold.

Table 1: Outer Loadings, Construct Reliability and Validity

Construct	Loading	CA (α)	CR (rho_a)	AVE
<i>Employees' Green Voice Behavior</i>		<i>0.883</i>	<i>0.885</i>	<i>0.588</i>
EGVB10	0.796			
EGVB2	0.802			
EGVB4	0.755			
EGVB5	0.725			
EGVB6	0.751			
EGVB7	0.777			
EGVB9	0.762			
<i>Inclusive Leadership</i>		<i>0.910</i>	<i>0.913</i>	<i>0.653</i>
IL1	0.721			
IL2	0.875			
IL3	0.795			
IL4	0.782			
IL5	0.852			
IL6	0.865			
IL7	0.752			
<i>Organizational Learning Culture</i>		<i>0.871</i>	<i>0.875</i>	<i>0.561</i>
OLC1	0.780			
OLC2	0.752			
OLC3	0.748			
OLC4	0.706			
OLC5	0.778			
OLC6	0.746			
OLC7	0.732			

CA: Cronbach's Alpha; CR: Composite reliability; AVE: Average variance extracted

Source: Author's calculation

The HTMT (Heterotrait-monotrait ratio) and the Fornell-Larcker criteria were then used to evaluate the discriminant validity (see Table 2). The Fornell-Larcker criterion test was performed by comparing the correlations between the latent variables to the square root of the AVE. Specifically, the square root of the AVE for each construct must be greater than the greatest correlation with any other construct. Table 2's results show that each item for each variable meets these criteria, meaning that each construct's square root of the AVE is greater than the others (Hair et al., 2017). Also, the HTMT ratio results provide additional evidence that the constructs have strong discriminant validity because all HTMT values are smaller than 0.850 (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

Fornell-Larcker Criterion				HTMT			
	EGVB	IL	OLC		EGVB	IL	OLC
EGVB	0.767	-	-	EGVB	-	-	-
IL	0.348	0.808	-	IL	0.389	-	-
OLC	0.716	0.344	0.749	OLC	0.788	0.385	-

Source: Author's calculation

4.2 Structural Model: Analyses of the structural model are based on the VIF, R^2 , and path coefficient values. Table 3 shows that VIF values are employed to establish connections between exogenous variables and ascertain the absence of substantial collinearity. The findings indicate that the VIF values fall below the critical value of 5.00 (Hair et al., 2014). Therefore, the proposed constructs do not exhibit multicollinearity.

Table 3: Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

	EGVB	OLC	IL
EGVB			
OLC	1.134		
IL	1.134	1.000	

Source: Author's calculation

The determinant coefficient test assesses the precision of the model's predictive value, which represents the collective influence of exogenous and endogenous variables. The predictive accuracy of this research model increases with value (Hair et al., 2017). The obtained R-square values are presented in Table 4. As indicated by the results, IL accounted for 53% of EGVB and 12% of OLC. Though the IL affects EGVB significantly, there might be other factors other than IL, that affect OLC significantly.

Table 4: R-square Test

	R ²	R ² adjusted
EGVB	0.525	0.521
OLC	0.118	0.115

Source: Author's calculation

In Table 5, the results show that IL substantially enhances EGVB ($\beta = 0.116$; $p = 0.013$). H_1 is therefore approved. In other words, IL encourages employees to act in a green voice. Likewise, IL greatly enhances OLC ($\beta = 0.344$; $p = 0.000$). Therefore, H_2 is also recognized, indicating that inclusive leaders foster a culture of learning where staff members feel free to express their thoughts. Since OLC significantly improves EGVB ($\beta = 0.676$; $p = 0.000$), H_3 is also acceptable. EGVB is therefore significantly influenced by the learning culture.

Table 5: Path Coefficient (Direct)

	β	σ	t	p
IL -> EGVB	0.116	0.047	2.487	0.013
IL -> OLC	0.344	0.063	5.434	0.000
OLC -> EGVB	0.676	0.039	17.285	0.000

Source: Author's calculation

Table 6 showed a significant result ($\beta = 0.348$, $t = 5.441$, $p = 0.000$) that showed the overall effect of IL on the EGVB outcome. Furthermore, it was discovered that IL had a significant direct impact on EGVB ($\beta = 0.116$, $t = 2.487$, $p = 0.013$). With OLC as the mediating variable, IL had a substantial effect on EGVB ($\beta = 0.233$, $t = 5.591$, $p = 0.000$). H_4 is therefore supported. Thus, the association between EGVB and IL is partially mediated via the OLC.

Table 6: Path Coefficient (Indirect)

Total effect (IL ->EGVB)			Direct effect (IL -> EGVB)			Indirect effect of IL on EGVB				Percentile bootstrap 95% confidence interval		
β	t	p	β	t	p	H4:	β	SE	t	p	Lower	Upper
0.348	5.441	0.000	0.116	2.487	0.013	IL -> OLC - > EGVB	0.233	0.042	5.591	0.000	0.143	0.312

Source: Author's calculation

The study model, which includes the path coefficients, is expressed as $OLC = 0.882 + 0.344 IL$ and $EGVB = 0.475 + 0.116 IL + 0.676 OLC$, as in Figure 3, based on the analysis.

Figure 3: Tested Model (Structural)

Source: Author's calculation

5. Discussion

The objective of the study was to investigate how IL affects EGVB and how OLC act as a mediator. The finding supports the hypothesized relationship, suggesting that employees who perceive their leaders as inclusive are more likely to proactively express environmentally oriented suggestions and concerns. This finding can be explained through the lens of SET, by voluntarily offering suggestions aimed at improving environmental sustainability, employees reciprocate IL behaviors, thereby strengthening the social exchange relationship. In the context of the tourism and hospitality industry, where frontline employees closely interact with operational processes and environmental resources, IL plays a crucial role in encouraging employees to speak up about sustainability-related issues. This finding is consistent with earlier studies that when workers believe that their leaders will appreciate their contributions and listen to them with respect, they are more likely to use green voice (Nguyen et al., 2025). Therefore, IL gives workers the interpersonal basis to bring up environmental concerns that could otherwise be viewed as dangerous or disruptive.

Then, the results demonstrate a statistically significant relationship between IL and OLC, indicating that IL plays a critical role in shaping a learning-oriented organizational environment. This finding can be effectively explained through the lens of SLT. Inclusive leaders act as salient social models within organizations by openly soliciting input, valuing diverse perspectives, and encouraging experimentation and dialogue. Through repeated observation of these behaviors, employees learn that knowledge sharing, questioning existing practices, and learning from mistakes are not only acceptable but encouraged. This supports the claim that IL encourage ongoing education, information exchange, and group problem-solving (Nemhard & Edmondson, 2006; Hirak et al., 2012). Inclusive leaders create an environment that encourages experimentation and organizational learning by respecting varied viewpoints and promoting participatory decision-making (Ashikali et al., 2021).

Next, the findings reveal that OLC has a significant influence on EGVB, underscoring the pivotal role of OLC in encouraging employees to proactively express green ideas and concerns. This result is consistent with research that indicates proactive environmental activities are encouraged by companies with good learning cultures (Jiang & Men, 2017). A learning culture makes it clear that the company encourages experimentation and information sharing, which makes it easier for staff members to and green activities.

Lastly, the mediation analysis demonstrates that OLC significantly mediates the relationship between IL and EGVB, indicating that IL influences EGVB by shaping a learning-oriented organizational culture. Though the effect is relatively low, OLC contributes to mediating the relationship between IL and EGVB. That also implies some other factors might strongly contribute to ensuring relationship between IL and EGVB. Therefore, by encouraging psychological safety, transparency, and trust, inclusive leaders may improve learning processes and provide staff members with the institutional support and self-assurance they need to use their green voice. This mediation effect supports past findings that leadership activities have an impact on employee outcomes due to cultural characteristics (Zhang et al., 2021). Consequently, one of the most important ways that IL converts into long-lasting employee behaviors is via cultivating an OLC.

6. Contribution of the Study

This study adds to the body of knowledge on OLC, IL, and EGVB in several ways. First, the study expands on the use of SET by demonstrating that IL has a favorable impact on EGVB (Blau, 1964). Through equity, transparency, and acknowledgement, inclusive leaders instill a feeling of responsibility and reciprocity in their workforce. Employees are more willing to participate in optional activities like green voice, which help the company and its sustainability objectives, in return for the support they get (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Afterwards, the discovery that IL greatly improves OLC adds to the expanding corpus of research that connects contextual and cultural enabling leadership styles (Hirak et al., 2012). This finding implies that leaders act as role models who uphold learning-oriented norms by promoting cooperation, information exchange, and experimentation, in line with social SLT (Bandura, 1977). These practices are observed and internalized by employees, strengthening the OLC.

Subsequently, the research demonstrates that OLC is a strong predictor of EGVB. By showing that a learning-oriented culture not only fosters creativity and adaptability but also gives staff members the confidence to voice environmental concerns, which adds to the body of research on green behavior (Li et al., 2020). In theory, this establishes OLC as a crucial contextual mechanism that converts leadership actions into environmentally beneficial results.

Then, this study increases knowledge of EGVB by combining SET and SLT to explain how IL promotes environmentally proactive employee behavior through OLC. By extending SET to the field of environmental sustainability, it shows how EGVB serves as a kind of positive reciprocity in response to IL. This broadens SET to incorporate environmentally conscious voice behaviors in addition to conventional

performance and civic behaviors. Then, by displaying that OLC is a crucial social environment through which IL influences employee behavior, the study improves SLT. It emphasizes how EGVB is encouraged by learning norms, modeling, and reinforcement processes, which enhance SLT-based explanations of pro-environmental behavior in businesses.

Furthermore, through the integration of SET and SLT, this study offers a dual-theoretical framework that explains how EGVB is taught and maintained inside businesses as well as why employees engage in it. This study expands on previous research that focused on transformational or ethical leadership in environmental contexts (Robertson & Barling, 2017) by demonstrating that inclusivity is also crucial for promoting sustainability-related voices.

In practice, the results indicate that companies looking to improve EGVB should invest in building a strong OLC in line with IL development since systems and procedures that promote education, information exchange, and experimentation must be in place to support leaders who exhibit inclusivity. By doing this, companies may foster an atmosphere where workers are encouraged to treat others with inclusivity and feel comfortable sharing green behaviors.

7. Conclusion and Future Research Directions

The results of this study show that IL plays a vital role in shaping employees' willingness to speak up for environmentally friendly practices. The findings confirmed that the measures used were reliable and valid, the model had strong predictive power, and the links between the variables were statistically significant. Overall, the study highlights that when leaders practice inclusiveness and cultivate learning, employees are more empowered and motivated to contribute to sustainability goals within their organizations.

Despite its contributions, this work contains a few shortcomings that open up new research directions. Importantly, OLC was found to partially mediate the relationship between IL and EGVB, suggesting other unexamined mechanisms may also explain this relationship. Future research should include other mediators like psychological safety, green self-efficacy, and perceived organizational support, through which IL promotes EGVB. Looking ahead, since this study was carried out in the hospitality sector, it would be valuable to test the model in different industries. Researchers might also consider using longitudinal or experimental approaches to better capture how leadership and culture evolve in shaping employees' sustainable actions.

Although CMB was not an issue, this study used self-reported data. Future research should include multi-source data collecting methodologies, such as asking for IL ratings from employees, EGVB assessments from supervisors, and OLC metrics combined at the team or organizational level. In addition, exploring boundary conditions such as company size, leadership experience, or external environmental pressures could reveal when and where IL is most effective. Finally, combining surveys with qualitative methods like interviews or case studies would help bring employees' lived experiences to the surface and offer a richer picture of how IL fosters meaningful contributions to sustainability.

Appendix

Total Variance Explained						
Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.661	33.312	33.312	8.661	33.312	33.312
2	3.566	13.717	47.029			
3	1.867	7.180	54.210			
4	1.611	6.198	60.407			
5	1.376	5.292	65.699			
6	1.026	3.946	69.645			
7	.802	3.085	72.730			
8	.768	2.954	75.684			
-	-	-	-			
-	-	-	-			
26	.135	.519	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

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